

FT-IR Spectroscopic Studies on Aleuritic Acid

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FT-IR spectra of different forms of aleuritic acid have been studied in the region 400–4000 cm^{-1} . Difference spectra in the case of *threo*-aleuritic acid indicate that the purity of the acid depends on the solvent used for crystallization.

Aleuritic acid (9*RS*,10*RS*,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid) is obtained in approximately 20% yield from the alkaline hydrolysis of lac resin¹. The naturally occurring acid is a racemic mixture having *threo*-configuration². It can be readily converted to its *erythro*-isomer by a number of procedures³. Both *threo*- and *erythro*-acids have proved to be important starting materials for the synthesis of a wide variety of bioactive compounds including JH analogs, prostanoic synthon, organic nitrates and tetrazoles⁴.

While it is relatively easy to obtain a pure form of *erythro*-aleuritic acid (m.p. 121°) by recrystallization from ethyl acetate, it has been observed that *threo*-aleuritic acid, commonly crystallized from EtOAc, has an m.p. of 97.5°. Recrystallization from distilled water yields *threo*-aleuritic acid having m.p. 101°, although in greatly reduced yield (40%). Because *erythro*-aleuritic acid as well as a number of synthetic compounds are obtained from *threo*-aleuritic acid, a thorough investigation on the profile of the starting material becomes necessary. Since DSC (differential scanning calorimetry) profiles depict a clear picture of the presence of any impurities in a given material. Goswami *et al.*⁵ recently studied the DSC melting curves of the different forms of aleuritic acid and concluded that crystallization from boiling water gives the purest form of *threo*-aleuritic acid.

IR spectroscopy being a useful tool in the determination of purity, quantitative analysis and production control⁶, it was thought worthwhile to investigate the various forms of aleuritic acid, taking into account the multiple advantages⁷ of FT-IR spectroscopy over conventional dispersive IR techniques.

Results and Discussion

Easwaran *et al.*² studied aleuritic acid by dispersive IR and concluded that *erythro*-isomer shows a single carbonyl absorption at 1695 cm^{-1} , whereas the *threo*-isomer shows two carbonyl bands at 1725 and 1655 cm^{-1} . The FT-IR spectrum, using 'centre of gravity' technique to determine peak position, shows the carbonyl absorption of *erythro*-aleuritic acid to be more precisely at 1700 cm^{-1} . 'Centre of gravity' technique computes the centre of area of a specified segment of a band using least-square algorithms to yield extremely precise frequency and bandwidth measurements in FT-IR spectroscopy⁸. The FT-

IR spectrum of *threo*-aleuritic acid shows the two C=O stretching peaks at 1719 and 1658 cm^{-1} .

Spectral subtraction is another extremely useful technique⁹ in FT-IR spectroscopy, in which a difference spectrum is obtained by digitally subtracting a spectrum *n* from another spectrum *n*+1. This allows one to see small differences between the two spectra which may not be apparent in the raw spectra and is frequently employed to isolate spectral features, detect impurities and remove solvent bands (in solution spectra). The difference spectrum obtained by subtracting the FT-IR spectrum of *threo*-aleuritic acid (crystallized from H₂O) from that of *threo*-aleuritic acid (crystallized from EtOAc) shows prominent peaks at 3482 cm^{-1} , attributable to dimeric, H-bonded hydroxyls, at 2962, 2917 and 2849 cm^{-1} due to aliphatic C–H symmetrical and asymmetrical stretching vibrations. A prominent differential at 2349 cm^{-1} does not appear to be an overtone or a combination band and is unexplainable, unless one considers the presence of an acetylenic artifact. A peak at 1735 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of an ester linkage, possibly a δ -lactone. A smaller peak at 1662 cm^{-1} is indicative of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl stretch. A band at 1468 cm^{-1} is characteristic of $-\text{CH}_2-$ deformation superimposed on a C–CH₃ deformation (asymmetrical) while that at 1056 cm^{-1} indicates C–O stretch and C–OH bending of primary open-chain saturated alcohol. The prominent peak at 721 cm^{-1} is due to C–H deformation about a C=C (*cis* only) superimposed with rocking vibrations of $-(\text{CH}_2)_n-$ where $n \geq 4$.

The overall picture seems to agree with the contention of Goswami *et al.*⁵ that *threo*-aleuritic acid recrystallized from H₂O is the purest and most suitable for the synthesis of fine chemicals. The higher yield and lower m.p. of *threo*-aleuritic acid recrystallized from EtOAc may be due to the presence of excipients consisting of long-chain alcohols, hydroxy acids and their esters (possibly lactones) together with their mono-olefinic derivatives. The formulation of IS specifications for different grades of aleuritic acid being manufactured by industry may be a step in the right direction.

Experimental

Naturally occurring DL-*threo*-aleuritic acid (m.p. 101°),

isolated from shellac¹⁰ was converted to its *erythro*-isomer by treatment with HBr/AcOH followed by alkaline hydrolysis of the bromoacetate with KOH (1%). Acidification with glacial acetic acid and recrystallization from EtOAc gave the *erythro*-isomer (m.p. 121°).

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. FT-IR(KBr) spectra were recorded on a Bomem-Michelson MB-100 spectrophotometer equipped with a laser source, KBr beamsplitter and DTGS detector. The instrument was set for 10 scans at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution with cosine apodisation in the mid-ir region, 400–4000 cm⁻¹, using Bomem Easy (ver. 1.5) and Matrix Plotter software.

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